

THEORETICAL COMPARATIVE SURVEY INTO STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF ENGLISH AND ARABIC PHRASAL VERBS

Yodgorova Shokhsanam Rakhmatali qizi,

Teacher

Termiz state university,

Surkhandarya, Uzbekistan

E - Mail: YodgorovaShR@mail.ru

Abstract

This article sets the target on doing typological comparison of two unrelated languages like English and Arabic with clear contrastive analysis of their idiomatic properties encompassing phrasal verbs and their word class verbs based on the lexical, semantic and stylistic features of idiomatic equivalency. The research is related to the problems of translation of phrasal verbs based on the comparison of that is the core of universal culture. Comparative analysis of semantic and lexical usage of phrasal verbs in the short stories, in particular setting semantic survey to full or partial equivalence between English and Arabic phrasal verbs. The content of the article starts with the brief description phraseology and its main assumptions as a theoretical discipline and sets on the practical analysis over phrasal verbs.

Keywords: Phraseology, comparative typology, translation, linguaculturology, pragmatics, semantics, phrasal verbs, idiomatic expressions

Introduction

Today, the full vision of the whole world is focused to the new Uzbekistan, the country owning progressive changes in the full phase of civilization of science expansion, is being admitted globally. Primarily, the civilian growth of the country is getting onward with the necessity of high skilled professionals who are able to formulate the actual development of country by confronting the upgrading levels of development Linguistic sciences. Responsiveness of linguistic science in recent decades more and more is paid to the translation problems of phraseological units, in particular phrasal verbs. It is conditioned by the fact that phrasal verbs are inseparable parts of human societies pertaining to the good form of cultural identity and common-ground dialogues among different nations. They form social and mental values of different human societies in great extent. The

topicality of the problems of understanding the idiomatic languages of the representatives of related and unrelated language even caused the emergence of a new linguistic trend – Contrastive Phraseology. Thus, the topicality of the research is conditioned by the following factors:

- a) Insufficient study of the problem of understanding, comparing and translating phrasal verbs into unrelated languages based on the extra linguistic properties conveying the message of certain from idiomatic units comparing two different languages from different language families.
- b) The research is related to the problems of translation of phrasal verbs based on the comparison of that are the core of universal culture;
- c) Comparative analysis of semantic and lexical usage of phrasal verbs in the short stories, in particular setting semantic survey to full or partial equivalence between English and Arabic phrasal verbs. The linguist's level of knowledge also leaves its impacts on the translation of the phraseological units into other unrelated languages. It is a constant struggle for the philologist to take extreme care for exactitude in his message conveying since the phrasal verbs are enriched with all the necessary peculiarities of its source language. In addition to that, the decoding phrasal verbs request detailed understanding and mastery of the owner's history, culture, dialects, names, and historical events in it for good interpretation.

The wealth of meaning contained in phrasal verbs, which are derived from numerous cultural and social terms can be translated only by sound dialectic imitation of that region relating to their history, culture, and geography of the as well as the language of science they contribute. Concerning to the abovementioned arguments, the several amount of the researchers, who fixed their methodical procedures in this arena, grown for the recent of two decades, which the lexical issues of comparing and translating phrasal verbs in the context has been held on the center of many discursive debates of majority contrastive linguists and phraseologists like Aarts, B, Abboud, P, Abdelhafiz O, Al-bayyatiy T, Al-bustaanii F. A, Al ghalaayiniy M, Ali A. S. M, Al-jaahiz, A. A, Alkhuli, M. A, Al-Kufaishi, A, Al-Qinai, J, Armstrong, K, Austin, J. L, Awwad, M, Azzaro G, Baker M, K. Dukes, Barber C, Bataineh, R. F, Beate Hampe, Belkacemi C, Bell, R, Ahmed Sharafeddin, Abo Baker Ali, Alsaleh Brakhw, Munif Zarirruddin Fikri bin Nordin, and and othe

1. Phraseology: Main assumptions and general concepts

1.1. Definition and general concept

The phraseology of a living language is a part of the linguistic picture of different societies in which their usage of language represents their way of thinking, ideological beliefs, cultural principles, dialectological domination, social relations, aesthetic and religious views in the reflection of phraseological units. It is essential to notify that the study to outlining phraseological units constitutes different viewpoints about the description of phraseology:

The Cambridge Advanced Learners Dictionary delineates the word “phraseology” as “the way in which language is used, especially in the choice of words and expressions whose meaning cannot be predicted from the usual meanings of its constituent elements.” According to Cain, Oakhill, and Lemmon (2005), phraseology denotes “the study of figurative expressions that usually can be interpreted literally relied on the nonliteral implication when used in a specific context” (p.66).

Moreover, in this field Grant and Bauer (2004) offered more technical explanation that the term Phraseology investigates a wide variety of different types of multiword units. They believe this term is supposed more open and restricted categorical features. They consider the phraseology carries different figurative patterns like metaphors, similes, and proverbs belong to the category of

“nonliteral” or figurative language which is difficult to interpret and to learn because they do not mean what they literally state.

Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia represents the etymology of the word phraseology, which the term originated from the Greek word (φράσις) phrasis, means "mode of communication" and -λογία -logia, "study of") is an approach which specializes to study and investigate such abovementioned ready – made word combinations of linguistic image of different human societies.

According to Charles Bell “Phraseology as a linguistic branch owns the unchanging periodical process on fixative character of idioms, collocations, phrasal verbs, and other types of multi-word lexical units (often collectively referred to as phrases), in which the component parts of the expression carry more specific meaning than predictable form of direct meanings when used independently”. Besides these different technical terminologies, the term “phraseology” is widely used in many theoretical fields. The meaning of phraseology, conversely, is not made clear in most literature whose target of discussion is phraseology itself. It is frequently occupied for arranged that everyone knows what phraseology means. Nevertheless, in fact, different interpretations have been proposed by different scholars or in different fields.

For case in point, Teliya (2005:55) realizes phraseology as “a domain of linguistic study which to a high degree illustrates the correlation between language and culture”. Apart from such a particular viewpoint required in studies which have specific needs, the term phraseology is given a general and broad definition. Instantly, Cowie defines it as “the study of the structure, meaning and use of word combinations” (1994: 68).

Gries (2008:4) also gives a broad definition of phraseology: “the co-occurrence of a form or a lemma of a lexical item and any other kind of linguistic elements (word/grammatical patterns)”. The tendency of future research seems to welcome a more general definition of phraseology, because it is taken as a superordinate term to encompass a number of phenomena. Some researchers have attempted to set out the conditions that a phraseological unit has to meet. For example, Waibel (2007:5) summarizes five such conditions, including their “multi-word character, lexicalization, fixedness, institutionalization and non-compositionality”. Amongst these, non compositionality is not necessarily required, since it can be taken as a continuum with degrees of opaqueness.

Broukal and Woods (1990:189) deliberate the phraseology as “the expedition of structural combination of a verb + an adverb particle and sometimes the particle may be followed by a preposition”. They get on the research project to confirm the most active part of phrasal verbs is adverbial particles attached by prepositional verbs usually change the meaning of the verb they are connected. The same definition is given by Kollin (1982:12) when she states that “Phraseology is the common subject which investigates the structures in consisting of a verb combined with a preposition like word, known as particle”.

1.2. English phrasal verbs

Heckel suggests (1998: 45) that “phrasal verbs include both two-and three- word strings”. Examples of such phrasal verbs are “give up”, “look after”, and “hand in” in which include two strings while “put up with”, “give in to” and “put up for” include three strings.

Phrasal verbs are considered by Graver (1963: 261) as “semi compounds” whereas Palmer (1965:180) regards them as “single units in the grammar “. He gives reasons for naming them like that by saying that “there are severe collocation restrictions. We can give in but not give down. We can look after someone but not look before him”. He adds that phrasal verbs are “obviously semantic units” because ‘give in’ equals ‘yield’, ‘look after’ may be replaced by the literary ‘tend’, ‘put up’ has the meaning

of ‘invent’, and ‘put up with’ means ‘tolerate’. What has been stated by Palmer (1965) concerning the treatment of phrasal verbs as single units is quite true and has a solid basis simply because we have to place certain prepositions or adverbs after certain verbs in order to convey certain meanings or concepts. Despite the fact that phrasal verbs are very frequent form in spoken English, many ESL (English as a second language) students avoid using them just as many ESL teachers avoid teaching them. Concerning the number of phrasal verbs in English, Praninskas (1957:217) states that “no one knows how many two-word verbs there are in English but the number is very large”.

1.2.1. Classification of English phrasal verbs

Next we have to look at how we can use phrasal verbs and what their classification. The classification of a phrasal verb based on the usage can be either idiomatic (i.e. it has a special meaning) or non-idiomatic properties. With his distinctive linguistic experience, Hiltunen (1985) describes the phrasal verbs as multi-word verbs based on the theory drawn by Quirk.

I. Quirk’s classification

In his substantial previous analytic studies Quirk considers multi-word verbs consist of many different subcategories, and the category of phrasal verbs that is usually included within the broad concept of idiomatic meaning. Quirk classifies multi-word verbs into three major categories as they are:

1. Phrasal verbs (e.g. turn up),
2. Prepositional verbs (e.g. go in)
3. Phrasal-prepositional verbs (e.g. get away with).

In this definition, he suggests that a phrasal verb basically is made of “verb + adverb”, while a prepositional one consists of the construction through verb and preposition. He thinks that a phrasal-prepositional verb takes the formulaic shape like “verb + adverb + preposition”.

II. Dagut and Laufer’s classification

Dina Abdel (2015) in his abovementioned research workflow offers to address the classification of Dagut and Laufer (1985). Bearing in mind their classification as very precise and easy – to – follow Dina indicates their three categorical classification over phrasal verbs following:

1. Literal phrasal verbs (e.g., go out) whose meaning can be directly induced from their components
2. Figurative phrasal verbs (e.g., turn up) which have undergone a metaphorical shift of meaning
3. Completive phrasal verbs (e.g., burn down) in which the particle is linked to the result of the action involved.

III. Laufer and Eliasson’s classification

In the same vein, Dina keeps on the classifications suggested by two other linguists. They are Laufer and Eliasson (1993). Similarly close to Dagut and Laufer’s classification they also presented their close detailed classification:

1. Semantically transparent (direct meaning can be obscured)
2. Semitransparent (semi direct meaning can be obscured)
3. Semantically opaque (metaphorical shift can be obscured)¹

1.2.2. Word class (basic components) of English phrasal verbs

One student in a lesson joked: “Take any verb and any preposition, put it together, come up with an incomprehensible meaning and that's it - the phrasal verb is ready!” In some points there will be some truth in some joke that a phrasal verb may contain two main components: the verb and the particle

¹ Concerning these terms, see McArthur (1992:72ff.)

(preposition or adverb). Many prepositions and adverbs of the English language are “participants” of phrasal verbs and called mainly as particles.

Carnie and Andrew (2012) defines that a word class is a set of words that can own phrasing properties and features with their inflections and distributions in English grammar. The term "word class" is similar to the more traditional term constituents of something. But this term has been extraordinarily identified with the point of the componential parts that can be formulized into phraseological content. Kroeger and Paul states (2005) that modern lexicographers normally recognize four major word classes of phrasal verbs:

- Verbs
- Particles (mostly adverbial)
- Adverbs (mostly prepositional)
- Prepositions (mostly semantic figurative)
- Determine (mostly possessive)

But note that some grammarians use different systems and may recognize till six or seven different word classes with determiners and pronouns. According to Zwicky and Arnold (2006) linguists recognize that the above mentioned eight or nine type of word classes which were classified by Kroeger are drastically simplified. For example, “adverb” is to some extent a catch – all class that includes words with many different functions.

¹¹ Haiden. M. (2006) illustrates following schedule for clear distinction

PHRASAL VERBS

Adverbial	Prepositional	Particle
An adverbial phrase is a phrase that acts as an adverb in a sentence. Most often, the main element in an adverbial phrase is an adverb. However, the other words in the phrase can modify this adverb. An adverbial phrase can modify verbs, adjectives and adverbs. For example:	A prepositional phrase is a phrase made up of a preposition and its object. This object can be a noun, pronoun, gerund or even a clause. A prepositional phrase always starts with a preposition; its object always occurs after it. For example:	Particle phrase is a phrase that fit easily into the established system of idiomatic form with verbs and adverbial particles. Many linguists witnessed that this form of phrase building is completely idiomatic which the meaning cannot be decoded by the isolation of words in it. For example:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The policemen took the guilty inside the home - Lily fell down from the tree 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - John came here to apply for a job - Mr. Joseph tries to deal with the problem in time. - The court resulted in announcement on imprisonment of him 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Michelle turned his passport up from his office (turn up = finding something unexpectedly) - Hickney called in his neighbor. (Call in = ask for help)

1.3. Arabic phrasal verbs

Phrasal verbs in Arabic language

- Definition

It is worth noting that Arab scholars who dealt with the phenomenon of English phrasal verbs have given it equally in the Semitic notion on various labels in Arabic (Al-dahesh;2008). In the same vein to that definition Arabian linguist Heleil (2000) calls them as “Al Afghal al murakkaba” similar to Dahesh. Daud considers the phenomenon of phrasal verbs like **يلعب بيكرت** (verbal compound).

According to Heleil (2000) mostly, phrasal verb in Arabic is modified by the meaning of its preposition. Thus, each verb could have more than one meaning due to the preposition attached to it. For that reason famous grammarians of Arabic origin, like Ibn-Aqeel (1964: 498) and Al Ghalaiyini (2004:39) classify phrasal verbs in Arabic with the notion of transitive verbs based on the Heleil’s theory mentioning objects and preposition for semi – direct address. They are:

I. Phrasal verbs that pass on their objects by themselves

(الفعل المعتدي لوحده)

II. Verbs that pass on their objects through a preposition

(الفعل المعتدي بحر)

The transitive verbs, as Heliel (2000:144) states govern either the accusative of a noun or a preposition with a noun in the genitive case or not the accusative, which means that these verbs “pass on their objects through a preposition. For example:

رجع الى بلاده (He came back to his hometown)

1 - I *believe in* God. (امنت بالله; Haywood and Named; 1993: 413)

2 - He *came with* a thing. (أتى بشيء)

3 - I was *angry with* you. (غضبت عليك)

4 - I *stayed with* them a whole year. (لبثت عندهم سنة كاملة)

5 - I *awoke in* the morning. (تنبهت في الصباح)

6 - He *arose at* dawn. (قام عند الفجر)

7 - They *bowed down* to the God. (سجدوا لله Thackston , 2000 : 236)

8 - He *pointed to* the woman. (أشار الى المرأة)

As far as the Arabic language is concerned poetic language, there exist many constructions in which verbs are followed by prepositions such as:

- to eat from - يأكل من
- to look at - ينظر الى

The leading study in this regard was conducted by Lentzner (1977) in his doctoral dissertation entitled Semantic and Syntactic Aspects of Arabic Prepositions in which he assigns a chapter to explore the verb-preposition structures in Arabic (pp. 155 – 195). Given the importance of the profound insights considered in such a chapter, it merits being summarized. Moreover, Arabic phrasal verbs have been profoundly investigated by numerous linguists also. Two most famous of them are: Abboud and McCarus (1968), have taken up the issue from the verb standpoint. Abboud and McCarus (1968) observe that there exist two kinds of verb-preposition constructions in Arabic; idiomatic and non-idiomatic.

In their monolingual Arabic-Arabic dictionary (The Contextual Dictionary of Idiomatic Expressions of Arabic language) Siinii, Hussain and Aldoush (1996) put together more than 2000 Arabic idiomatic expressions collected from a wide range of ancient and modern Arabic literature, representing all the aspects of such a phenomenon in the Arabic language. This book will be reviewed in more detail in section six of this Chapter when the issue of PVs in Arabic will be attended to.²

² Ali, A. S. M. (2004). A study of antonymous and synonymous couplings in Arabic with reference to translation. Babel, 50 (4), 346-360

Moreover, in his attempt to further compare English idioms with their Arabic Counterparts, Awwad (1990) makes the point that English idioms can be lexemic as in (hammer and tong), phraseological as in (to fly off the handle) and proverbial as in (don't wash your dirty linen in public). Like English Arabic lexemic idioms can be verbal, nominal, adjectival, and adverbial (p. 58). Yet, "Arabic verbal lexemic idioms do not occur with particles" (p. 58). Therefore, the Arabic equivalent for (he broke into the house)

دخّل البيت غنوة or اقتحم البيت (meaning: he entered the house by force).

Arabic prepositions perform different functions in the sentence. Firstly, they serve to link a noun to another noun or a noun phrase to reveal the relationship between the two. It is worth noting that the parts; functions of prepositions and usages of prepositions are clarified with English examples alongside word for word transliteration. Transliteration is rather significant in order to illustrate how prepositions are used in Arabic.

To sum up, Current dissertation devotionally set the research under the focus of the research on translation and contrastive comparison of phrasal verbs and their inner parts between two unrelated languages regarded as one of the most fundamental problems of contrastive phraseology. Being a new linguistic trend, contrastive phraseology studies the relationship between phraseological units of diverse languages owning different linguistic universals as well as the units which contain dissimilar linguacultural origin. Taking into consideration those abovementioned factors, the researcher did the research on comparing the phrasal verbs and their word classes between English and Arabic language and completed it with high contributive properties which was shown the following conclusive declines:

1. The research is done at the cross – phase of various linguistic disciplines such as translation studies, contrastive linguistics, linguaculturology, cognitive stylistics and lexicology. Being one of the methodological principles of the anthropocentric paradigm, the interdisciplinary approach makes it possible to do a comprehensive and consistent analysis of phrasal verbs in the short stories from the position of comparing and contrast on two unrelated languages.
2. The basic analytic mechanism of the research were contrastive phraseology and translatology regarded as a combination of various linguistic units that through phraseological units conveys socio – cultural information with stable concept of intercultural relevance considering to be a basic unit of international dialogue, being a constituent part of the national conceptosphere;
3. On cultural values and conceptual properties of phrasal verbs, the research ascribed the object and subject of the research as the reflection of individual specificity, mentality, outlook and views.

References

1. . Aarts, B. (1989). Verb-Preposition Constructions and Small Clauses in English J. Linguistics (25), 277-290
2. Aarts, B. (1997). English Syntax and Argumentation. London: University College. Abboud, P. F., & McCarus, E. N. (1968). Elementary Modern Standard Arabic. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press
3. . Abdel-Hafiz, A.-S. (2003). Pragmatic and Linguistic Problems in the Translation of Naguib Mahfouz's The Thief and the Dogs: A Case Study. Babel, 49 (3), 229- 252.
4. . Al-bayyatii, T. (1982). What Pupils Need in English. Beirut: Al-NahDah Institution for Cultural Services.
5. Al-bustaanii, F. A. (1963). Munjid al-Tulaab (in Arabic). Beirut: al-maTba3atu

alkatholiikyyah

6. . Al-ghalaayini, M. (1986). Jaami' al-dduruus al-'arabiyyah (in Arabic). Beirut: almaktabatu al-3aSriyyah.
7. . Ali, A. S. M. (2004). A study of antonymous and synonymous couplings in Arabic with reference to translation. *Babel*, 50 (4), 346-360
8. . Al-jaaHiZ, A. A. (1932). al-bayaan wa-altabyiin (in Arabic) Cairo: al-maTba3atu alraHmaanyyah
9. . Al-jurjaanii, A. A. (1991). ?asraar al-balaaghah (in Arabic). Beirut: Daar al-jiiil.
10. . Al-jurjaanii, A. A. (n.d.). dalaailu al-ijaaZ (in Arabic). Cairo: maTba3atu majallati al-manaar.
11. . Al-jurjaanii, A. M. (1969). kitaab al-ta3riifaat (in Arabic). Beirut. maktabat lubnan. Alkhuli, M. A. (1999). *Comparative Linguistics: English and Arabic*. Jordan: Alfalah House.
12. . Al-Kufaishi, A. (2004). Translation as a learning and teaching strategy. *Babel*, 50 (1), 45-59.
13. . Al-Qinai, J. (2000). Translation Quality Assessment: Strategies, Parameters and Procedures. *Meta*, XLV (3), 497-519.
14. . Beate Hampe, J. (1997). Towards a solution of the phrasal verb puzzle: Considerations on some scattered pieces. *Lexicology*, 3/2, 203-243.
15. . Belkacemi, C. (1998). Prepositions with verbal functions in Arabic. *Orientalia Suecana* (47), 13-20.
16. Bell, R. (1991). *Translation and Translating: Theory and Practice*. London and New York: Longman.
17. Bennett, D. C. (1975). *Spatial and Temporal Uses of English Prepositions: An Essay in Stratificational Semantics*: London: Longman Group Limited.
18. Berman, L. A., & Kirstein, L. (1996). *Practical Idioms: Using Phrasal Verbs in Everyday Contexts* (Second ed.). Illinois: National Textbook Company (NTC).
19. . Cowie, A. P. (1993). Getting to grips with phrasal verbs. *English Today* 36, 9 (4), 38-41.
20. Crowley, T., Lynch, J., Siegel, J., & Piau, J. (1995). *The Design of English: An introduction to descriptive linguistics*. Auckland: Longman Paul.